

A Study on Customer Attitude With New Trend in Mobile Marketing

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Abstract

In modern business, the product will not be able to survey without aggressive marketing. Mobile marketing is a market strategy which is a multi-channel aimed at reaching many customers through the mobile devices. I.e., through the website, email, SMS, MMS, social Media and apps. It allows the marketer to reach a highly targeted audience. Mobile marketing also helps in Customer Relationship Management (CRM). Now, most of the people are very attached to their smart phones, so mobile marketing is more friendly and familiar to the end user. The research work was aimed at studying the customer attitude with the new trend in mobile marketing. The sample size of the study was 60 and the data was collected in the Tirunelveli district.

Introduction

According to the trends, a note is businesses and marketers today is go mobile or go home. The market has now been inclined to mobile and to the extent that the perception of the people has now been driven by it giving rise to more mobile marketing strategies. It has been estimated that by 2019, the percentage of the population using mobile will reach 5 billion marks from 4.93 billion in 2018. With this exponential rise, it has become significantly important to use mobile marketing techniques to become visible online and make the market presence for your business. Mobile Marketing is the interactive multichannel promotion of products or services for mobile phones and devices, smart phones and networks. Mobile marketing channels are diverse and include technology, trade shows or billboards. Mobile marketing is a way in which technology can be used to create personalized promotion of goods or services to a user who constantly connected to a network. Mobile advertising is a subset of mobile marketing. Therefore, it is necessary to keep yourself updated with the latest trends going to dominate mobile marketing in 2018 to get your business on board. So the study is based on the customer attitude with the emerging trends in the mobile marketing.

Objectives of The Study

- To study the awareness of mobile marketing in Alangulam area.

- To analyze the influence of mobile marketing in the purchase decision.
- To know about the kind of products bought by utilizing digital channels.

Scope of the Study

The suggestion from the study is based on the responses given by the consumers in a specific area. This study will be helpful in getting an insight into and impact of mobile marketing in customer purchase decision.

Research Methodology

The study carried out with both primary and secondary data. The primary data was collected through a structured questionnaire from the sample of 50 respondents from the specified area. The samples were collected by using non-probability sampling that is convenient sampling method. The sample was used for further analysis. Secondary data is also being collected from articles, journals and magazines, etc.

Table 1 Shows the Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	References	Percentage
Age	Below25	6	20
	25-35	12	40
	35-45	8	26.7
	Above 45	4	13.3
	Total	30	100
Gender	Male	19	63.3
	Female	11	36.7
	Total	30	100
Level of Education	High school graduate, diploma (or) similar	6	20
	Technical (or) vocational training diploma	13	43.4
	Bachelor's degree (or) Master's degree	7	23.3
	Doctorate	4	13.3
	Total	30	100
Job	Government job	4	13.3
	Private job	13	43.4
	Self-employed		20
	Retired	4	13.3
	Others	3	10
	Total	30	100
Income Level	Less than 20000	7	23.3
	20000-40000	15	50
	More than 40000	8	26.7
	Total	30	100

The above table shows 20% of the respondents belongs to the age group of below 25. 40% of the respondents belong to the age groups of 25-35. 26.7% of the respondents belong to the age groups of 35-45. 13.3% of the respondents belong to the age groups above 45. The above table shows 63.3% of the respondents are male. 36.7% of the respondents are female. The above table shows that 20% of the respondents are high school graduate, diploma (or) similar. 43.4% of the respondents are technical or vocational training diploma. 23.3% of the respondents are bachelor's degree of master's of degree. 13.3% of the respondents are doctorate. 13.3% of the respondents are doing the government job. 43.4% of the respondents are the private job. 20% of them are self-employed. 13.3 % of the respondents are retired. 10% of the respondents during other jobs. 23.3% of the respondents have income less than 20000. 50% of the respondents are having income 20000-40000. 26.7% of the respondents have income more than 40000.

Table 2 Type of Smart Phone used by the Respondents

S.no	Smart phone used	Respondents	Percentage
1	iPhone	6	20
2	Android	9	30
3	Windows mobile	5	16.7
4	Others	10	33.3
	Total	30	100

- 20% of the respondents are using the iPhone.
- 30% of the respondents are using android.
- 16.7% of the respondents are using windows mobile.
- 33.3% of the respondents are using others.

Table 3 Which form of Mobile Advertising Having You Experienced the Must?

S.no	Experience	Respondents	Percentage
1	SMS/ MMS	6	20
2	Banner advertisement	9	30
3	QR code	4	13.3
4	Mobile video	5	16.7
5	Location-based	4	13.3
6	Others	2	6.7
	Total	30	100

- 20% of the respondents are experienced in mobile advertising in SMS/MMS.
- 30% of the respondents are most experienced in mobile advertising in the banner advertisement.
- 13.3% and 16.7% of the respondents are experienced in mobile advertising in QR code and mobile video.
- 13.3% and 6.7% of the respondents are experienced in mobile advertising in location-based and others.

Findings

- Majority of the respondents 40% belong to the age group of 25 to 35.
- Majority of the respondents are male with 63.3%
- Majority of the respondents are technical or vocational training diploma with 43.3%.

- Majority of the respondents are the private job with 43.4%.
- 50% of the respondents have income level 20000-40000
- Majority of the respondents are the smart phone used with 33.3%.
- Majority of the respondents are mobile advertising experienced on banner advertising with 30%.

Suggestion

- Mobile marketing is probably by far the most fickle of the forms of marketing because this customer base will alter rapidly influenced by outside influences. Outdated or irrelevant technology may hurt your business, so it is very important to remain updated on new developments to keep up a competitive edge.
- The notion of mobile marketing is to pay attention to overall customers, as opposed to gaining brand new ones. The relationships we may have already built will likely be more receptive in our mobile marketing updates than customers. Quite often, mobile marketing that may be directed at customers is regarded as spam.

Conclusion

Even in our increasingly mobilized world, your website remains a vital hub. Given the vast array of mobile devices currently on the market and in the hands of consumers, mobile site development efforts are almost equally varied. That's why we spent a lot of time discussing the pros and cons of some approaches. But bear in mind, this space is evolving with nearly the same speed as the devices themselves. You'll want to make ongoing education a priority so you can keep up with your audience.

References

- Ashraf, M.F., & Kamal, Y. (2010). Acceptance of mobile marketing among university student S.Mustang journal of Business and Ethics, 1, 9-29. Retrieved from
- Baker, M.J. (2003). The marketing book. Oxford: Butterworth-Heinemann. Retrieved from
- Baker, W.B. (2014). The complications of doing mobile marketing legally. Journal of Internet law,17(8),13-25. Retried from
<http://ezproxy.snhu.edu/login?url=http://search.proquest.com/docview/815245286?http://ezproxy.snhu.edu/login?url=http://search.proquest.com/docview/1501614290?accountid3783>.
- [http://www.amazon.com/The-marketing-book-fifth-edition idp10750655364](http://www.amazon.com/The-marketing-book-fifth-edition-idp10750655364).

Web Sources

- <http://erepo.usiu.ac.ke/handle/11732/3410>
- <http://technians.com/blog/mobile-marketing-trends-in-2018/>
- <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/m/mobile-marketing.asp>
- <http://www.ijirst.org/articles/IJIRSTV2I10099.pdf>
- <http://www.cauverycollege.ac.in/is305.pdf>
- <https://www.safaribooksonline.com/library/view/mobile-marketing-an/9781118388440/chap04-sec037.html>